

Uniqueness of the Dirichlet Problem for Graphical Self-Shrinkers

By *Sawyer Jacobson*

Let Ω be a bounded domain in Euclidean space \mathbb{R}^n , with boundary $\partial\Omega$ of class C^2 . A smooth hypersurface $\Sigma \subset \mathbb{R}^{n+1}$ is called a self-shrinker if it satisfies the equation

$$H = \frac{1}{2}\langle x, \nu \rangle,$$

where H denotes the scalar mean curvature and ν is a Gauss map. It has long been recognized that self-shrinkers serve as models for Type I singularities of the mean curvature flow, and their classification remains a problem to which considerable effort has been devoted.

The present work concerns itself with hypersurfaces of the form $\Sigma = \{(x', U(x')) : x' \in \Omega\}$, whose study reduces, as we shall recall, to the analysis of a quasilinear elliptic partial differential equation for U . The Dirichlet problem for this equation asks of us to find $U \in C^2(\bar{\Omega})$ satisfying the self-shrinker equation throughout Ω and the boundary condition $U = \Gamma$ on $\partial\Omega$ simultaneously.

It is not apparent in reviewing the literature that the question of uniqueness for this problem has been addressed directly. We therefore show here that the Dirichlet problem for graphical self-shrinkers admits at most one solution. The argument proceeds by linearization, after which a maximum principle constrains the difference between any two solutions to vanish identically.

1. Preliminary Results

We assume throughout, unless explicitly stated to the contrary, that Ω is a bounded domain in \mathbb{R}^n whose boundary is of class C^2 . The proof of uniqueness which we shall give depends on reformulating the self-shrinker equation, originally posited in terms of mean curvature H and the position vector x , as a quasilinear partial differential equation. The subsequent elementary result is the form to which the analysis of later sections may be applied directly.

Proposition 1.1. *A graphical surface $\Sigma = \{(x_1, \dots, x_n, U(x_1, \dots, x_n)) : (x_1, \dots, x_n) \in \Omega\}$, satisfies the self-shrinker equation $H = \frac{1}{2}\langle x, \nu \rangle$ if and only if U solves*

$$\mathcal{S}(U) := \operatorname{div} \left(\frac{\nabla U}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla U|^2}} \right) - \frac{U - x' \cdot \nabla U}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla U|^2}} = 0, \quad (1)$$

with $x' := (x_1, \dots, x_n)$.

Proof. The unit normal vector $\nu = \frac{(-\nabla U, 1)}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla U|^2}}$ and the position vector to Σ is $x = (x', U(x'))$. As established in [1],

$$H = \frac{1}{2} \operatorname{div} \left(\frac{\nabla U}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla U|^2}} \right).$$

Direct computation yields $\langle x, \nu \rangle = \frac{U - x' \cdot \nabla U}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla U|^2}}$, hence

$$\operatorname{div} \left(\frac{\nabla U}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla U|^2}} \right) = \frac{U - x' \cdot \nabla U}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla U|^2}}.$$

As is evident by rearrangement, $\mathcal{S}(U) = 0$. □

2. Linearization and a Maximum Principle

We now turn to the comparison of two solutions of the graphical self-shrinker equation. The method of linearization will be employed to show their difference satisfies a second-order linear equation in divergence form.

Lemma 2.1. *Let $U_1, U_2 \in C^2(\bar{\Omega})$ be two solutions to (1). Define $W := U_1 - U_2$ and $U_t := U_2 + tW$ for $t \in [0, 1]$. Then W satisfies $\operatorname{div}(a \cdot \nabla W) - b \cdot \nabla W - cW = 0$, in Ω , where*

1. $a(x') = \int_0^1 J_\chi(\nabla U_t(x')) dt$ is symmetric and uniformly positive definite,

2. $b^i(x') = - \int_0^1 \frac{x_i + \frac{(U_t - x' \cdot \nabla U_t)(U_t)_i}{1 + |\nabla U_t|^2}}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla U_t|^2}} \in L^\infty(\Omega)$,

3. $c(x') = \int_0^1 \frac{dt}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla U_t|^2}} \geq (1 + \|\nabla U_1\|_{L^\infty}^2 + \|\nabla U_2\|_{L^\infty}^2)^{-\frac{1}{2}} > 0$.

Proof. We define $\chi(p) := \frac{p}{\sqrt{1 + |p|^2}}$ and $\psi(x', u, p) = \frac{u - x' \cdot p}{\sqrt{1 + |p|^2}}$. By Proposition 1.1, each U_i satisfies $\operatorname{div}(\chi(\nabla U_i)) = \psi(x', U_i, \nabla U_i)$. So,

$$\operatorname{div}(\chi(\nabla U_1) - \chi(\nabla U_2)) = \psi(x', U_1, \nabla U_1) - \psi(x', U_2, \nabla U_2). \quad (2)$$

Proceeding,

$$\chi(\nabla U_1) - \chi(\nabla U_2) = \int_0^1 \frac{d}{dt} \chi(\nabla U_t) dt = \int_0^1 J_\chi(\nabla U_t) \cdot \nabla W dt = a \cdot \nabla W. \quad (3)$$

That a is uniformly positive definite follows from [2]. Furthermore,

$$\psi(x', U_1, \nabla U_1) - \psi(x', U_2, \nabla U_2) = \int_0^1 \left(\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial U} |_{U_t, \nabla U_t} W + \sum_i \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial p_i} |_{U_t, \nabla U_t} \frac{\partial W}{\partial x_i} \right) dt. \quad (4)$$

Computing directly, $\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial u} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + |p|^2}} > 0$, and

$$\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial p_i} = \frac{-x_i(1 + |p|^2) - (u - x' \cdot p)p_i}{(1 + |p|^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} = - \frac{x_i + \frac{(U_t - x' \cdot \nabla U_t)(U_t)_i}{1 + |\nabla U_t|^2}}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla U_t|^2}}.$$

Since $U_1, U_2 \in C^2(\bar{\Omega})$, ∇U_1 and ∇U_2 are bounded on $\bar{\Omega}$; by the triangle inequality, ∇U_t is bounded uniformly in t . As such, the denominators are bounded below by 1, and the numerators are bounded above, from which $b \in L^\infty$. It follows that $\psi(x', U_1, \nabla U_1) - \psi(x', U_2, \nabla U_2) = c(x')W + b(x') \cdot \nabla W$, with c and b as stated. The positivity of c follows from $\sqrt{1 + |\nabla U_t|^2} \leq \sqrt{1 + \|\nabla U_1\|_{L^\infty}^2 + \|\nabla U_2\|_{L^\infty}^2}$. Substituting (3) and (4) into (2) yields

$$\operatorname{div}(a \cdot \nabla W) = cW + b \cdot \nabla W. \quad \square$$

We record next a maximum principle valid for any linear elliptic equation of this type, noting that the zeroth-order coefficient must be bounded below by a positive constant and that the first-order coefficients lie in L^∞ . Though the substance of this lemma is essentially well known, we include a proof for completeness.

Lemma 2.2. *Let $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be bounded. Suppose $W \in C^2(\Omega) \cap C^0(\bar{\Omega})$ satisfies*

$$\sum_{i,j} a^{ij}(x) \partial_{ij} W + \sum_i \tilde{b}^i(x) \partial_i W - c(x)W = 0 \text{ in } \Omega, \quad (5)$$

where $a = a^{ij}$ is a symmetric and uniformly positive definite matrix, $\tilde{b}_i \in L^\infty(\Omega)$, and $c \geq c_0 > 0$ in Ω . If $W = 0$ on $\partial\Omega$ then $W \equiv 0$ in Ω .

Proof. Suppose for contradiction $M := \max_{\bar{\Omega}} W > 0$. Since $W = 0$ on $\partial\Omega$, the maximum must be attained at some $x_0 \in \Omega$. At such a point, $\nabla W(x_0) = 0$ and $D^2W(x_0)$ is negative semi-definite. Evaluating (5) at x_0 ,

$$0 = \sum_{i,j} a^{ij}(x_0) \partial_{ij} W + \sum_i \tilde{b}_i(x_0) \partial_i W - c(x_0)M = \text{tr}(a(x_0)D^2W(x_0)) - c(x_0)M. \quad (6)$$

The positive definiteness of $a(x_0)$ in tandem with the negative semi-definiteness of $D^2W(x_0)$ ensures that their product has a non-positive trace. Conversely, $c(x_0)M \geq c_0M > 0$. Accordingly (6) forces $0 \leq -c_0M < 0$, a contradiction. The same argument can be applied to $-W$ by symmetry to dispose the possibility that the minimum is negative. We conclude that $W \equiv 0$. \square

3. Uniqueness of Graphical Self-Shrinkers

It remains only to verify that the coefficients arising from the difference of two solutions to the graphical self-shrinker partial differential equation satisfy the hypotheses of the aforementioned maximum principle, after which uniqueness follows.

Theorem 3.1. *Let $U_1, U_2 \in C^2(\bar{\Omega})$ be solutions to the graphical self-shrinker equation over Ω , with $U_1 = U_2 = \Gamma$ on $\partial\Omega$. Then $U_1 \equiv U_2$ in Ω .*

Proof. We set $W = U_1 - U_2$. By Lemma 2.1, W satisfies $\text{div}(a \cdot \nabla W) - b \cdot \nabla W - cW = 0$ in Ω , with a being uniformly positive definite, $b \in L^\infty$, $c \geq c_0 > 0$ and $W|_{\partial\Omega} = 0$. Expanding,

$$\sum_{i,j} a^{ij} \partial_{ij} W + \sum_j \left(\sum_i \partial_i a^{ij} - b^j \right) \partial_j W - cW = 0.$$

That this is precisely the form of (5) follows from the observation that $\nabla U_1, \nabla U_2 \in C^1$, which is a consequence of $U_i \in C^2$ and thus, $\sum_i \partial_i a^{ij} \in L^\infty$. Lemma 2.2 implies $W \equiv 0$ in Ω , As was to be shown. \square

References

- [1] T. H. Colding and W. P. Minicozzi II, Generic mean curvature flow I: generic singularities, *Ann. of Math.* (2) 175 (2012), no. 2, 755–833.
- [2] David Gilbarg, Neil S. Trudinger, Elliptic Partial Differential Equations of Second Order (Reprint of the 1998 Ed.), *Springer Berlin, Heidelberg* (2001).